

When AI Enters Federal Statistics: A Crosswalk Between Data Quality and AI Trustworthiness Frameworks*

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2026-02-25

Abstract

Two frameworks are relevant when artificial intelligence is used in federal statistical work: FCSM 20-04 (*A Framework for Data Quality*) for evaluating data product quality, and NIST AI RMF 1.0 (*Artificial Intelligence Risk Management Framework*) for evaluating AI system trustworthiness. Neither references the other, and no published crosswalk connecting them was identified in a literature search. NIST maintains twelve crosswalks to other frameworks, but none from the federal statistical community. Without a shared crosswalk, each agency must independently interpret how the two frameworks relate, producing inconsistent approaches that undermine the coherence both frameworks are designed to provide. A public crosswalk provides a common reference point: a consistent interpretation that practitioners can adopt, evaluate, and refine as both frameworks and operational experience evolve.

This article presents the first FCSM × NIST AI RMF crosswalk. Part I maps 11 FCSM dimensions and 7 NIST characteristics across five relationship types: 4 direct mappings where existing practice satisfies both frameworks, 3 partial or split mappings requiring judgment or decomposition, 3 distributed mappings where FCSM functionally addresses NIST concerns across multiple dimensions without naming them, and 4 FCSM-only dimensions outside NIST's scope. A companion appendix provides the complete subcategory-level mapping across all 72 NIST AI RMF subcategories, formalized as a graph database and validated for bidirectional consistency. Part II examines where framework-level mapping reaches its limits, particularly for AI-specific failure modes like confabulation that require domain-specific validation. Part III demonstrates two research implementations showing how the crosswalk tailors to different operational contexts.

1 Introduction

Two frameworks are relevant when artificial intelligence is used in federal statistical work: one for evaluating data product quality, the other for evaluating AI system trustworthiness. Neither references the other. No published crosswalk connects them.

The Federal Committee on Statistical Methodology published FCSM 20-04, *A Framework for Data Quality*, in September 2020. It organizes 11 quality dimensions under three domains (Utility,

*The views expressed are the author's own and do not necessarily represent the views of the U.S. Census Bureau or the U.S. Department of Commerce.

Objectivity, and Integrity) and provides the standard vocabulary for federal agencies evaluating data products ([Federal Committee on Statistical Methodology, 2020](#)).

The National Institute of Standards and Technology published the AI Risk Management Framework (AI RMF 1.0) in January 2023. It defines seven characteristics of trustworthy AI and organizes risk management through four core functions: GOVERN, MAP, MEASURE, and MANAGE ([National Institute of Standards and Technology, 2023a](#)).

As of February 2026, NIST's official crosswalk page lists twelve mappings between AI RMF and other frameworks: ISO/IEC standards, the EU AI Act, OECD AI Principles, and national AI governance bodies from Singapore, Korea, and Japan, among others. Every crosswalk addresses either international standards harmonization or regulatory alignment. None addresses federal statistical data quality ([National Institute of Standards and Technology, 2023b](#)). OECD and Eurostat have published guidance on AI in official statistics, but neither presents a dimension-level crosswalk to NIST AI RMF 1.0.

FCSM published FCSM 25-03, *AI-Ready Federal Statistical Data*, in 2025, extending the FCSM 20-04 framework to address AI systems consuming federal statistics ([Federal Committee on Statistical Methodology, 2025](#)). But FCSM 25-03 addresses one direction of the AI-statistics intersection (AI consuming data) without mapping to the AI risk management framework that addresses the other (AI producing or transforming data). The two communities, federal statisticians and AI risk management practitioners, are working in parallel without a shared reference for how their frameworks relate.

NIST AI RMF is voluntary; no statute compels its adoption. But the risks it addresses are not. AI systems that participate in the statistical production lifecycle, whether in data collection, processing, estimation, dissemination, or interpretation, introduce failure modes that can compromise the credibility of the resulting data products. An agency that uses AI without evaluating the system's trustworthiness does not avoid the risk; it avoids knowing about it.

This crosswalk establishes the connections between both frameworks so practitioners can apply them together, ensuring that AI-assisted statistical products are evaluated against both data quality standards and AI trustworthiness requirements consistently without duplicating effort. Sections 4 and 5 demonstrate the crosswalk in practice through two experimental implementations: an AI-assisted survey harmonization classification pipeline and an AI-mediated federal statistical data consultation system.

1.1 What Each Framework Covers

FCSM 20-04 organizes eleven quality dimensions under three domains: *Utility* (Relevance, Accessibility, Timeliness/Punctuality, Granularity), *Objectivity* (Accuracy & Reliability, Coherence), and *Integrity* (Scientific Integrity/Credibility, Transparency, Confidentiality,

Computer & Physical Security, Objectivity of Presentation). These evaluate properties of data products.

NIST AI RMF 1.0 defines seven characteristics of trustworthy AI: Valid & Reliable, Safe, Secure & Resilient, Accountable & Transparent, Explainable & Interpretable, Privacy-Enhanced, and Fair with Harmful Bias Managed. These evaluate properties of AI systems.

The frameworks operate on different axes: FCSM asks whether the output is fit for use; NIST asks whether the system that produced it is trustworthy. The crosswalk maps where these concerns overlap. Definitions of each follow.

1.1.1 FCSM 20-04: Data Quality for Federal Statistics

FCSM 20-04 was developed by a working group of the Federal Committee on Statistical Methodology, established under OMB’s Statistical Policy Directives. It provides a comprehensive inventory of data quality elements organized under three domains ([Federal Committee on Statistical Methodology, 2020, pp. 13–29](#)):

Table 1: FCSM 20-04 Utility Domain: the extent to which the data product is well-targeted to identified and anticipated needs

Dimension	Measures
Relevance	Fitness for user needs
Accessibility	Ease of obtaining and understanding data
Timeliness/Punctuality	Currency and delivery schedule
Granularity	Sufficient detail for intended use

Table 2: FCSM 20-04 Objectivity Domain: whether information is accurate, reliable, and unbiased

Dimension	Measures
Accuracy & Reliability	Closeness to true values; consistency of measurement
Coherence	Consistency across sources, methods, and time

Table 3: FCSM 20-04 Integrity Domain: maintenance of rigorous standards and protection of information

Dimension	Measures
Scientific Integrity/Credibility	Adherence to scientific methods; independence from inappropriate influence
Transparency	Open documentation of methods, sources, and limitations
Confidentiality	Protection of respondent information from unauthorized disclosure
Computer & Physical Security	Protection from unauthorized access, modification, or destruction
Objectivity of Presentation	Accurate, clear, unbiased presentation

The framework emphasizes that quality is fitness-for-purpose: the same data product may score high on one dimension and low on another, and managing trade-offs among dimensions is an explicit part of data quality practice ([Federal Committee on Statistical Methodology, 2020, p. 14](#)).

1.1.2 NIST AI RMF 1.0: Trustworthiness for AI Systems

NIST AI RMF was developed under the National Artificial Intelligence Initiative Act of 2020 ([National Artificial Intelligence Initiative Act of 2020, 2021](#)). It defines seven characteristics of trustworthy AI ([National Institute of Standards and Technology, 2023a, pp. 13–18](#)):

Table 4: NIST AI RMF 1.0 Trustworthiness Characteristics

Characteristic	Measures
Valid & Reliable	Correct and consistent system performance
Safe	Avoidance of harm to life, health, property, environment
Secure & Resilient	Resistance to attack and recovery from disruption
Accountable & Transparent	Attributable responsibility; documented methods and limitations
Explainable & Interpretable	Understandable operations; meaningful outputs in context

Characteristic	Measures
Privacy-Enhanced	Proper data collection, use, and retention
Fair with Harmful Bias Managed	Equitable outcomes across protected groups

Two features of the NIST framework matter for this crosswalk:

1. **Valid & Reliable is the base condition.** NIST’s own Figure 4 shows it as the foundation on which all other characteristics rest. An AI system cannot be meaningfully safe, fair, or explainable if it is not first valid and reliable.
2. **Accountable & Transparent is cross-cutting.** NIST depicts it as a vertical element that relates to all other characteristics. Transparency is not one concern among many; it is the condition that makes all other characteristics assessable.

The framework is explicitly voluntary, non-sector-specific, and designed for tailoring. NIST states that “rarely do all characteristics apply in every setting” and that organizations should balance characteristics based on context ([National Institute of Standards and Technology, 2023a, p. 14](#)).

2 The Crosswalk

FCSM 20-04 addresses fitness for use of data products (is the output suitable for its intended purpose?). NIST AI RMF addresses trustworthiness of AI systems (is the system safe, fair, and reliable?). Most pairs have some relationship, but the relationships vary in complexity and in how much additional work they require. Some FCSM dimensions have no NIST equivalent at all. Not all mappings will apply to every system; context determines which rows matter. The purpose of the crosswalk is not to reconcile the frameworks or collapse their distinct scopes, but to define how they must be co-applied when AI systems participate in federal statistical production workflows.

The crosswalk produces five types of mappings:

- **Direct (1:1):** Same concern, different vocabulary. Existing FCSM practice satisfies the NIST requirement at the data-quality evaluation layer. No additional work.
- **Partial:** The concepts overlap but do not fully cover each other. One framework’s dimension maps to part of the other’s, with scope left over on one or both sides. The work is judgment about where the overlap holds and where it does not.
- **Split (1:many or many:1):** Both frameworks name the relevant concepts explicitly but group them differently. One framework’s single dimension maps to multiple named concepts in the other. The work is reorganizing, not discovering.

- **Distributed:** One framework names a concern that the other addresses in practice but never identifies as a single concept. The functional coverage exists but is scattered across multiple dimensions without a unifying label. The work is assembling scattered practices into a coherent assessment and naming what has been unnamed.
- **FCSM-only:** NIST does not evaluate data product fitness. These dimensions have no NIST equivalent because they are outside the scope of AI system trustworthiness.

Table 5: Structural Signature of Each Mapping Type

Type	Both sides name it?	Full coverage?	Work required
Direct	Yes	Yes	None
Partial	Yes	No, incomplete overlap	Scope judgment
Split	Yes	Yes, different packaging	Reorganizing
Distributed	One side only	Yes, but unnamed	Assembly + naming
FCSM-only	One side only	No equivalent exists	N/A

These five categories emerged from observed patterns in the correspondences. The mapping focused on identifying plausible connections; where no connection is shown, it means none was found, not that none exists. This approach follows the methodology NIST itself prescribes: the AI RMF is designed for contextual application, with organizations expected to tailor the framework to their specific domain and document their reasoning ([National Institute of Standards and Technology, 2023a, pp. 2–3, 14](#)). The crosswalk is an evaluation framework translation, not an empirical validation study. Any framework translation requires interpretation, and this one is no different. The crosswalk reflects the current versions of both frameworks and the author’s best judgment about how they correspond. Practitioners applying it will bring their own institutional context, and their interpretations may reasonably differ. It will warrant revision as the frameworks are updated and as operational experience with AI in federal statistics accumulates.

This typology matters for practitioners. The goal is to minimize duplication: where existing FCSM practices already address a NIST concern, agencies should not build a parallel evaluation process. Where gaps exist, the crosswalk identifies targeted additional work rather than wholesale duplication. The table below classifies each pair; the detailed analysis follows.

Table 6: FCSM 20-04 / NIST AI RMF 1.0 Crosswalk

FCSM 20-04			
Dimension	NIST AI RMF Characteristic(s)	Mapping	Additional Work
Accuracy & Reliability	Valid & Reliable	Direct	None
Transparency	Accountable & Transparent	Direct	None
Confidentiality	Privacy-Enhanced	Direct	None
Computer & Physical Security	Secure & Resilient	Direct	None
Coherence	Valid & Reliable	Partial	Scope judgment
Scientific Integrity/Credibility	Valid & Reliable; Accountable & Transparent	Split (1:2)	Decomposition
Objectivity of Presentation	Accountable & Transparent; Fair with Harmful Bias Managed	Split (1:2)	Decomposition
Confidentiality; Computer & Physical Security; Accuracy & Reliability	Safe	Distributed	Assembly required
Transparency; Scientific Integrity	Explainable & Interpretable	Distributed	Assembly + computational interpretability
Survey methodology (not a named dimension)	Fair with Harmful Bias Managed	Distributed	Naming + explicit testing
Relevance	No NIST equivalent	FCSM-only	N/A
Accessibility	No NIST equivalent	FCSM-only	N/A
Timeliness/Punctuality	No NIST equivalent	FCSM-only	N/A
Granularity	No NIST equivalent	FCSM-only	N/A

2.1 Direct Mappings

Four pairs map directly. Existing FCSM practice satisfies the NIST requirement with no additional work.

Accuracy & Reliability / Valid & Reliable. Both ask whether outputs are correct and consistent. FCSM frames this as closeness to true values and measurement consistency; NIST frames it as intended performance and consistent results under expected conditions. Same concern, different language.

Transparency / Accountable & Transparent. Both require documenting methods, sources, limitations, and quality. The operational meaning is identical: document what you did, how you did it, and what the limitations are.

Confidentiality / Privacy-Enhanced. Both address protection of individual information from unauthorized disclosure. Scope differs (statistical disclosure versus broader data privacy) but the core concern is the same.

Computer & Physical Security / Secure & Resilient. Both protect systems from unauthorized access, modification, and destruction. NIST adds adversarial attack resistance and system resilience beyond traditional IT security.

2.2 Partial and Split Mappings

Four pairs overlap but require judgment or decomposition.

Coherence / Valid & Reliable (partial). FCSM coherence is a comparative measure: consistency across sources, methods, and time. NIST validity includes consistency but does not separately distinguish internal coherence from external validity. An AI system could pass NIST's validity requirements while producing outputs that are internally inconsistent across different runs or methods.

Scientific Integrity/Credibility / Valid & Reliable + Accountable & Transparent (split 1:2). FCSM bundles methodological soundness and shielding from inappropriate influence into one dimension. NIST splits these across two characteristics. No single NIST characteristic captures the full FCSM dimension.

Objectivity of Presentation / Accountable & Transparent + Fair with Harmful Bias Managed (split 1:2). FCSM's "accurate and clear" component maps to NIST transparency; FCSM's "without bias" component maps to NIST fairness. One FCSM dimension, two NIST characteristics.

2.3 Distributed Mappings

Three NIST characteristics are functionally addressed by existing FCSM practices but not named as single concepts. The work is largely already being done; the gap is consolidation and, in some cases, targeted extension.

Safe / Confidentiality + Computer & Physical Security + Accuracy & Reliability (distributed). FCSM's Confidentiality dimension exists specifically to prevent harm to respondents from unauthorized disclosure, including physical harm (e.g., exposure of domestic violence survivors, immigration status), economic harm (employment discrimination), and psychological harm (stigma from health or criminal justice data). Computer & Physical Security protects the systems that enforce these protections. Accuracy & Reliability prevents incorrect outputs from feeding bad policy decisions. These are safety functions in substance if not in name. When AI mediates access to statistical data, these existing concerns intensify: confidently wrong statistical guidance driving consequential policy or individual decisions, and compromised disclosure avoidance codebases. The additional work is consolidating these distributed protections into an explicit safety assessment and addressing AI-specific attack surfaces (adversarial queries, prompt injection) that FCSM did not anticipate.

Explainable & Interpretable / Transparency + Scientific Integrity (distributed). FCSM requires documentation of methods (Transparency) and methodological soundness (Scientific Integrity). Together these cover most of what NIST means by explainability. The gap is computational interpretability: understanding how the model arrives at its answer, not just documenting what was fed in and validating that the methodology is defensible. An LLM whose inputs, outputs, and methods are fully documented satisfies FCSM Transparency, but if its internal reasoning process remains opaque, it does not satisfy NIST Explainability. The additional work is targeted: adding model-level interpretability on top of existing documentation practices.

Fair with Harmful Bias Managed / Survey methodology (distributed). FCSM addresses demographic equity through survey design practices: oversampling, coverage adjustment, post-stratification. These are sophisticated, well-established practices that directly address the concern NIST names. But FCSM embeds them in methodology rather than naming fairness as a quality dimension. NIST requires explicit, proactive bias testing across protected characteristics as a system property. The additional work is making the implicit explicit: naming what is already being done and adding AI-specific bias testing (e.g., does the model classify questions about minority populations differently than majority populations?).

2.4 FCSM-Only Dimensions

Four FCSM dimensions have no NIST equivalent. These dimensions ask whether the data product actually serves the needs of the people who rely on it. NIST uses similar words ("relevant,"

“accessible,” “timely”) but means something different: properties of the risk management process, not properties of the data.

Relevance. FCSM asks whether the data product addresses user needs. NIST’s MAP function asks whether deployment context and intended uses are documented. One addresses output fitness; the other ensures organizational awareness. An AI system can satisfy every NIST trustworthiness characteristic while producing irrelevant outputs.

Accessibility. FCSM asks whether users can obtain and understand the data product. NIST uses “accessibility” in the context of workforce equity and inclusive design in the development process. Different construct entirely.

Timeliness/Punctuality. FCSM asks whether data is current and delivered on schedule. NIST calls for risk management that is “continuous, timely, and performed throughout the AI system lifecycle”: timeliness of governance, not timeliness of output.

Granularity. FCSM asks whether data provides sufficient detail for the intended use. NIST discusses disaggregation of accuracy measurements by demographic subgroup: granularity of evaluation, not granularity of output.

2.5 What the Crosswalk Shows

The crosswalk was formalized as a graph database (11 FCSM dimensions, 72 NIST subcategories, 104 correspondence edges) and checked for bidirectional consistency between Mapping A and Mapping B. The graph verification confirms that the encoded relationships are logically consistent across both directions; it does not validate whether the mappings themselves are correct. That validation came through the two implementations in Chapters 4 and 5, where construct-level mismatches surfaced and were corrected.

The practical value of this crosswalk is showing practitioners exactly where existing work counts and where targeted additional effort is needed, rather than treating FCSM and NIST as two separate evaluation regimes. Agencies with mature FCSM practices have already addressed most of what NIST AI RMF requires. The four direct mappings require no additional work. The partial and split mappings require judgment and decomposition but no new capabilities. The distributed mappings require consolidating existing practices and adding targeted AI-specific extensions, not duplicating evaluation effort. The FCSM-only dimensions remain essential regardless of AI involvement. An AI system can be fully trustworthy by NIST standards while producing outputs that are irrelevant, stale, or too coarse for any user’s needs.

3 The Specification Gap

3.1 The Gap Between Generic and Domain-Specific

The crosswalk in the previous chapter maps 11 FCSM dimensions and 7 NIST characteristics across five relationship types: direct, partial, split, distributed, and FCSM-only. The distributed mappings already identify where existing practice covers NIST concerns without naming them. But the crosswalk also reveals a practical limitation: the gap between system-level guidance and domain-specific application.

3.1.1 The AI-Specific Failure Mode in Statistical Work

Consider a concrete scenario. A federal agency uses a large language model to classify whether survey questions across two instruments measure the same construct, a common task in survey harmonization, data integration, and questionnaire design. The LLM examines question texts, response options, and contextual metadata, then produces a classification: “These questions are equivalent” or “These questions differ because of [specific barrier].”

FCSM 20-04 provides the vocabulary to evaluate the classification’s quality. Is it accurate? (Accuracy & Reliability.) Is it consistent with other assessments? (Coherence.) Was the method scientifically sound? (Scientific Integrity.) Are the results documented? (Transparency.)

NIST AIRMF provides the vocabulary to evaluate the AI system’s trustworthiness. Does it perform as intended? (Valid & Reliable.) Are its operations understandable? (Explainable & Interpretable.) Does it produce systematically biased results? (Fair with Harmful Bias Managed.)

NIST AI 600-1 (Generative AI Profile) explicitly identifies confabulation (“confidently stated but false content”) as an AI risk requiring continuous monitoring, runtime guardrails, and human-in-the-loop controls ([National Institute of Standards and Technology, 2024](#)). *Neither framework specifies what confabulation detection looks like in a particular federal statistical domain: what counts as a confabulated survey classification, what guardrails catch semantic smearing (the model confidently blurring distinctions between constructs that are actually distinct) in ACS consultation, or what “continuous monitoring” means when the outputs are statistical harmonization judgments rather than chatbot responses.*

We use the term **confabulation** throughout, consistent with NIST AI 600-1’s own usage. The colloquial term “hallucination” has become widespread in AI discourse but is imprecise; hallucination implies perception of something not present, whereas confabulation implies construction of false knowledge presented as real.

An LLM can assert with apparent certainty that two questions measure the same construct when they do not. It can propose a statistical bridge between concepts that don’t actually measure the same thing. It can generate plausible-sounding reasoning that cites nonexistent methodological

precedent. This is not measurement error in the FCSM sense; the input data is unchanged. It is not invalidity in the NIST sense; the system is performing the task it was designed to perform. It is a failure mode specific to AI systems operating in domains where the correctness of outputs requires domain expertise to verify. FCSM was not designed to detect this because FCSM addresses quality threats that arise from data collection, processing, and estimation, following the Total Survey Error framework and its extensions. The idea that the analytical tool itself might confabulate results with high confidence is outside the framework’s design assumptions.

NIST addresses confabulation explicitly: AI 600-1 identifies it by name and prescribes system-level controls: continuous monitoring, runtime guardrails, data provenance checks, and human-AI configuration to counter automation bias ([National Institute of Standards and Technology, 2024](#)). But these controls operate at the system level. NIST can tell you to monitor for confabulation. It cannot tell you what confabulation looks like when the domain is survey harmonization, because that requires knowing what survey harmonization is. “Continuous monitoring” for a chatbot means tracking user satisfaction and factual accuracy against a ground truth database. “Continuous monitoring” for an AI classifying whether two survey questions measure the same construct means, specifically: what multi-vendor agreement metrics? Expert review sampling? Construct validity checks against established measurement theory? NIST does not say, because NIST cannot say. The answer is domain-specific.

Neither framework ignores confabulation entirely. FCSM’s Scientific Integrity requires sound methods, which could include validating AI outputs. NIST’s Valid & Reliable includes robustness under unexpected conditions, which could include catching confidently wrong outputs. But neither specifies what those requirements mean in practice: FCSM does not say what “accepted scientific methods” look like when the analytical tool is an LLM, and NIST does not say what “unexpected conditions” to test for when the domain is survey harmonization. The gap is one of *specification*, not detection. Both frameworks name the concern; neither provides the protocol to evaluate it in a particular statistical AI application. Filling that gap requires both frameworks simultaneously, plus domain-specific validation methods that neither provides on its own.

Because framework mapping cannot catch domain-specific confabulation, you need human subject matter expertise with grounded, domain-specific validation protocols. The next two chapters demonstrate what those look like: one for an AI-assisted survey harmonization pipeline and one for an AI-mediated statistical consultation system, showing how the crosswalk tailors to each operational context.

4 Implementation A: AI-Assisted Survey Harmonization

The crosswalk in the preceding chapters maps FCSM dimensions to NIST characteristics at the framework level. This chapter and the next demonstrate how the crosswalk tailors to two different

AI applications in federal statistical work, each with different operational contexts, risk profiles, and quality concerns. In both cases, the crosswalk guided design decisions from the beginning, not just evaluation after the fact.

The two implementations share the same crosswalk foundation but differ in which cells matter most. This is exactly how a crosswalk should work: the structural mapping is stable, but the emphasis shifts based on what the AI system actually does.

4.1 Context

4.1.1 The Problem

Consider 7,000 questions spread across a sample of 47 surveys from the U.S. Census Bureau’s demographic programs. The surveys span economic, health, education, housing, and other topics; the classification method is not specific to any single domain. Many questions overlap across surveys, covering demographics, income, household composition, and employment status, but no systematic assessment exists of which questions could be consolidated or used as bridge variables for cross-survey data enrichment. At this scale, manual crosswalk work is not feasible. This implementation uses AI to do the initial screening.

4.1.2 What Was Built

An AI-assisted classification pipeline where three independent large language models from different commercial vendors (Anthropic Claude, OpenAI ChatGPT, Google Gemini) each classify question pairs from two surveys for harmonization potential. Each pair gets a feasibility rating and written reasoning. The results are presented as a prioritized list for SME review. The pipeline operates offline on publicly available survey questions; no respondent data is processed.

4.1.3 Why This Design

Every design choice maps to a specific quality concern in the crosswalk. Multi-vendor independence means results cannot be artifacts of one vendor’s training data (FCSM Coherence, NIST Valid & Reliable). Randomized presentation order controls for primacy and recency bias (FCSM Accuracy & Reliability, NIST Valid & Reliable). Structured arbitration with mandatory written reasoning makes every decision traceable (FCSM Scientific Integrity, NIST Accountable & Transparent). Public code, prompts, and data provide full reproducibility (FCSM Transparency, NIST Accountable & Transparent). Configuration files ensure parameters are visible and consistent (FCSM Accuracy & Reliability, NIST Valid & Reliable).

4.1.4 What Was Found

The pipeline produced a prioritized list of 170 candidate harmonization questions for expert review. Initial rater agreement was moderate (Fleiss' $\kappa = 0.537$ for feasibility, 0.611 for barrier classification); structured arbitration improved this to near-perfect agreement ($\kappa = 0.843$), confirming that the task is well-defined and that independent models converge when given a protocol for resolving ambiguity. Behavioral analysis confirmed the three vendors make genuinely independent judgments: synthesis rates and selection patterns differ significantly across vendors, evidence against correlated training-data bias. Total API cost was under \$100 (labor and infrastructure excluded).

4.2 Tailored Crosswalk

Table 7: Tailored Crosswalk: AI-Assisted Survey Harmonization Classification

Pipeline Quality Measure	FCSM Dimension(s)	NIST Characteristic(s)
Multi-vendor rater agreement (3 models, 3 vendors)	Accuracy & Reliability; Coherence	Valid & Reliable
Randomized presentation order	Accuracy & Reliability	Valid & Reliable
Multi-vendor arbitration (3 arbitrators resolve disagreements)	Accuracy & Reliability; Coherence	Valid & Reliable; Accountable & Transparent
Structured arbitration protocol (must select/synthesize with reasoning)	Scientific Integrity/Credibility; Transparency	Accountable & Transparent; Explainable & Interpretable
Public code, prompts, and data	Transparency; Accessibility	Accountable & Transparent
Deterministic pipeline (fixed seeds, checkpoint/resume)	Accuracy & Reliability; Scientific Integrity	Valid & Reliable
Construct validity checks	Coherence; Scientific Integrity	Valid & Reliable
Behavioral analysis of vendor patterns	Coherence; Accuracy & Reliability	Fair with Harmful Bias Managed; Accountable & Transparent

Pipeline Quality Measure	FCSM Dimension(s)	NIST Characteristic(s)
Human SME review protocol	Accuracy & Reliability; Scientific Integrity	Valid & Reliable

4.3 What This Implementation Shows

Valid & Reliable is a gate, not a dial. If the AI assigns wrong classifications, every downstream decision is contaminated. The multi-vendor agreement metrics provide indirect evidence; the SME review protocol provides the human-in-the-loop quality check to flag confident confabulations.

The bias concern here is epistemic, not demographic. The pipeline evaluates whether pairs of survey questions measure the same construct. The bias risk is that vendors share training-data blind spots, not that the system treats demographic groups differently. The behavioral analysis, showing genuinely different decision patterns across vendors, is the direct evidence against that risk.

The honest limitation is confident confabulation: an LLM can assert that two questions measure the same construct when they do not. Multi-vendor independence makes this less likely but not impossible. The SME review protocol exists specifically to catch these cases.

5 Implementation B: AI-Mediated Statistical Consultation

5.1 Context

5.1.1 The Problem

The American Community Survey (ACS) is the largest household survey in the United States, covering more than 40 topics across every geographic level from nation to census tract ([U.S. Census Bureau, 2025](#)). The data drive federal funding allocations, civil rights enforcement, redistricting, and policy analysis at every level of government. But the data are not straightforward for non-experts, and without proper guidance on fitness for use, users can draw wrong conclusions or make incorrect interpretations from otherwise valid data.

LLMs offer a way to bridge this gap, translating natural language questions into API calls and presenting results with context. But the data still require interpretation, and an LLM can confidently confabulate that interpretation, or ground itself in web data that is not authoritative. A model might make claims about ACS 1-year data for a 30,000-population county (which does not exist) or compare estimates across overlapping time periods (which is methodologically invalid).

5.1.2 What Was Built

A Model Context Protocol (MCP) server that mediates access to Census API data through three knowledge representation approaches, evaluated in a controlled experiment:

- **Control:** A baseline LLM (Claude Sonnet 4.5) with access to Census API tools but no domain knowledge beyond its training data.
- **RAG (Retrieval-Augmented Generation):** The same LLM with the same tools, plus 311 document chunks retrieved from three ACS source documents (354 pages total) via semantic similarity search.
- **Pragmatics:** The same LLM with the same tools, plus 36 curated expert judgment items delivered via MCP at the point of statistical reasoning. Each item encodes a specific decision rule traced to source documents with page-level citations.

The pragmatics approach implements an “always-ground” protocol: the agent must consult methodology guidance before interpreting any data retrieval, ensuring expert judgment is present at the point of decision rather than retrieved after the fact.

5.1.3 Why This Design

The three-condition experiment isolates the effect of knowledge representation. All conditions have identical tool access (Census API), identical model capability (Sonnet 4.5), and identical evaluation instruments. The only variable is how domain knowledge reaches the model. This directly tests whether the form of knowledge delivery matters for statistical consultation quality.

5.1.4 What Was Found

Pragmatics significantly outperformed both control and RAG across a five-dimension Consultation Quality Score rubric evaluated by nine LLM judges from three vendors (three vendors, three models). Vendor diversity reduces the risk of correlated bias in evaluation, though overlapping public training corpora mean that full statistical independence across vendors cannot be assumed. The largest differences appeared on uncertainty communication and fitness-for-use guidance, the two dimensions most directly related to preventing misuse of statistical estimates. The effect was strongest on small-area queries, exactly where population thresholds, margin of error reporting, and product selection matter most. Curated expert judgment at the point of decision outperformed bulk document retrieval: 36 pragmatics items beat 311 RAG chunks. The problem is not insufficient information but insufficient judgment. Whether the pragmatics approach scales beyond the topics tested here to the full breadth of ACS subject matter, and eventually to other federal surveys, is an open question. The benchmarking infrastructure used in this evaluation provides the tools to identify gaps, test extensions, and measure improvements iteratively as coverage expands.

5.2 Tailored Crosswalk

Table 8: Tailored Crosswalk: Census MCP Evaluation

Quality Measure	FCSM Dimension(s)	NIST Characteristic(s)
Accuracy of data values	Accuracy & Reliability; Objectivity of Presentation	Valid & Reliable
Completeness of response	Relevance; Granularity	Valid & Reliable
Uncertainty communication	Accuracy & Reliability; Transparency; Scientific Integrity	Accountable & Transparent; Explainable & Interpretable
Appropriate sourcing	Accessibility; Transparency; Scientific Integrity	Accountable & Transparent
Fitness-for-use guidance	Relevance; Coherence; Transparency	Explainable & Interpretable
Grounding (binary gate)	<i>Structural design property</i>	Valid & Reliable
Claim-level fidelity verification	Accuracy & Reliability	Valid & Reliable
Claim traceability to source	Transparency; Accessibility	Accountable & Transparent
Multi-vendor LLM judges	Accuracy & Reliability; Coherence	Valid & Reliable; Fair with Harmful Bias Managed
Model independence (Stage 3 verifier differs from Stage 1 generator)	Scientific Integrity / Credibility	Valid & Reliable
Deterministic methodology compliance	Accuracy & Reliability; Scientific Integrity	Valid & Reliable
Human expert validation protocol	Accuracy & Reliability; Scientific Integrity	Valid & Reliable

5.3 What This Implementation Shows

Explainability matters more here than in Implementation A. Implementation A operates in batch: experts review classifications after the fact. Implementation B operates in real time: a user asks a

question and gets an immediate answer with no independent means of verification. This makes NIST’s Explainable & Interpretable characteristic operationally critical. The pragmatics approach addresses this through fitness-for-use guidance that explains not just what the data says but why the user should or should not trust it for their specific purpose.

6 Comparing the Implementations

Table 9: Comparison of Implementation A and Implementation B

Dimension	Implementation A (Harmonization)	Implementation B (Consultation)
Primary NIST gate	Valid & Reliable (classification accuracy)	Valid & Reliable (pipeline fidelity)
Bias type	Epistemic (vendor classification patterns)	Epistemic (semantic smearing from training data)
Safety applicable?	Low: classifies public survey metadata, not respondent data. No reidentification pathway.	Low for reidentification (pre-tabulated, disclosure-reviewed data). Real risk: confabulation leading to bad decisions (see discussion).
Privacy applicable?	No (public survey metadata)	Emergent: disclosure avoidance workflow risk (see discussion)
Explainability emphasis	Low (batch, expert-reviewed post hoc)	High (real-time, user has no independent verification)
Confabulation risk profile	Correlated vendor bias leading to wrong harmonization paths	Semantic smearing leading to wrong statistical guidance
Confabulation mitigation	Multi-vendor agreement + SME review	Curated expert judgment at point of decision + pipeline fidelity

Dimension	Implementation A (Harmonization)	Implementation B (Consultation)
Grounding compliance	N/A (not applicable to classification rubric)	Binary protocol gate: treatment conditions grounded in authoritative sources, control is not. Verified through tool-call auditing.
Evaluation cost	<\$100 API (classification pipeline)	~\$15 API (3-stage evaluation pipeline)

6.1 Reading the Comparison

The Safety row reveals why tailoring is not optional. Implementation A classifies public survey metadata: question texts, response options, and survey instrument names. There is no respondent data, no reidentification pathway, and no safety risk in the NIST sense. The worst outcome of a classification error is a wrong entry on an expert review list, caught by human review.

Implementation B operates on public aggregate statistics that have already passed through Census Bureau disclosure avoidance review. The API returns pre-tabulated tables, not individual records, and the AI cannot compose novel cross-tabulations that bypass that review. The reidentification risk from ACS data alone is minimal. A more credible threat narrative involves combining ACS aggregates with breached databases containing individual-level data (names, addresses, phone numbers), but this narrative collapses on inspection: if an attacker already has individual-level identity data from a breach, the marginal value of locating that person within aggregate census tract statistics is negligible. The identity is already compromised. The real privacy threat in the AI era comes from the breached databases themselves, not from aggregate survey statistics, and conflating the two misdirects attention from where it is actually needed.

The safety concern for *this* system is more mundane but more real: confabulation leading to bad decisions. If an AI consultation system confidently misinterprets ACS data, presenting 1-year estimates for geographies below the population threshold, ignoring margins of error on small-area estimates, or comparing estimates across overlapping time periods, users can make consequential decisions based on wrong statistical guidance. This is Safety in the NIST sense: the system's operation can cause harm through confidently wrong interpretation of otherwise valid data. The mitigation is the same Valid & Reliable gate that governs both implementations, but the real-time, user-facing nature of Implementation B makes the consequences of failure more immediate.

The Privacy row extends this logic. Neither implementation collects personal data, so Privacy-Enhanced in the NIST sense does not apply in its traditional formulation. But

Implementation B introduces an emergent risk: if AI assists in developing or updating disclosure avoidance codebases (suppression rules, noise injection, rounding), semantic smearing could compromise the systems that protect respondent confidentiality upstream of publication. The privacy risk is not in the public data themselves but in the integrity of the systems that produce them.

The same two findings recur in both implementations: Valid & Reliable is a binary gate (if the system confabulates, nothing else matters), and domain-specific validation is required that neither framework provides on its own. The same structural mapping produces different emphasis patterns when applied to different operational contexts, and both implementations cost under \$100 in API fees to evaluate (labor and infrastructure excluded).

7 Conclusion

This article presented the first crosswalk between FCSM 20-04 and NIST AI RMF 1.0, two frameworks relevant to AI-assisted federal statistical work, one for data product quality and one for AI system trustworthiness, that until now had no published mapping connecting them.

The crosswalk presented here maps 11 FCSM dimensions and 7 NIST characteristics across five relationship types. The structural overlap is more extensive than a naive comparison would suggest. Four pairs map directly. Three partial mappings require judgment but no new capabilities. Three NIST characteristics (Safety, Explainability, Fairness) are functionally addressed by existing FCSM practices distributed across multiple dimensions; the gap is consolidation and naming, not building from scratch. Four FCSM Utility dimensions have no NIST equivalent because NIST does not evaluate data product fitness. Neither framework specifies what confabulation detection looks like in specific federal statistical domains. A standalone subcategory-level mapping accompanies this article as Appendix A and is intended for submission to both the NIST crosswalk program and to FCSM for review.

7.1 Implications for Agencies, Risk Management Practitioners, and FCSM

Statistical agencies adopting AI must continue to evaluate data products under FCSM while adding NIST AI RMF evaluation for the AI systems themselves. NIST AI RMF is voluntary; no statute compels its adoption. But the risks it addresses are not. AI systems that participate in the statistical production lifecycle introduce failure modes that can compromise the credibility of the resulting data products. An agency that uses AI without evaluating the system's trustworthiness does not avoid the risk; it avoids knowing about it, and undetected risks compound as AI takes on more of the production lifecycle. AI does not create an exemption from data quality requirements; it creates new threats that must be managed within the existing framework, supplemented by AI-specific risk management that FCSM was not designed to provide.

AI risk management practitioners working with federal data need to recognize that NIST characteristics have pre-existing, highly developed specifications in the statistical context. “Validity” means something much more specific than generic AI validity. “Transparency” carries regulatory force under the Information Quality Act and the OPEN Government Data Act (*Information Quality Act, 2000*; *OPEN Government Data Act, 2019*). And the primary bias concern is often epistemic rather than demographic: whether the AI systematically favors certain classifications, not whether it discriminates against protected groups.

FCSM has demonstrated leadership in extending its framework to AI contexts with FCSM 25-03, which addresses AI systems consuming federal data. The other direction, AI systems producing, transforming, or classifying statistical data, remains unaddressed. This crosswalk offers a starting point for that work.

7.2 You Do Not Need to Wait

The survey harmonization pipeline (Section 4) and the statistical consultation system (Section 5) demonstrate that agencies can apply the crosswalk now, without waiting for an official mapping, an OMB directive, or a completed stakeholder review. But the value of the crosswalk in these implementations was not limited to after-the-fact compliance evaluation. It guided the work from the beginning: framing threats to statistical validity, shaping architectural decisions, defining what needed to be measured, and structuring the tests that would provide evidence of trustworthiness.

This matters more, not less, as AI systems take on semi-autonomous or autonomous roles in statistical production. When an AI system generates code, performs analysis, or classifies data with decreasing human oversight at each step, the planning discipline becomes the primary control. The crosswalk is not a catchall that requires anticipating every risk upfront. It is a design tool. Start with what the system is trying to accomplish, identify the quality dimensions and trustworthiness characteristics at stake, build with those in mind, and trace new components back to the risks they introduce. NIST’s own GOVERN-MAP-MEASURE-MANAGE cycle describes exactly this: an iterative process where risk management is concurrent with development, not a post-hoc audit.

The credibility of statistical data products has always depended on the rigor of the processes that produce them. When those processes include AI, demonstrating that the system has appropriate controls, checks, and balances to produce reliable, high-quality results is what makes the data credible: not surface-level assurance, but evidence that the production system is trustworthy.

The point is not perfection. It is intent and method. “Valid and Reliable” means something different for an LLM classifying survey questions than for an LLM advising users on ACS estimates. Those differences must be worked out by practitioners who understand both the statistical domain and

the AI system, informed by both frameworks. This crosswalk provides the structural bridge; the implementations show what crossing it looks like.

AI in federal statistics is new enough that every application will involve learning. The crosswalk and its tailored implementations are offered as a starting point, open for interpretation, review, and adjustment as the field develops experience with these systems.

Use of AI in This Work

This article was developed with the assistance of large language models (Anthropic Claude, Google Gemini, OpenAI ChatGPT) for brainstorming, drafting, and iterating prose. All analytical conclusions reflect the author's professional assessment. All AI-generated content was reviewed and validated by the author.

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Appendix A: Standalone FCSM × NIST AI RMF Crosswalk Mapping

February 25, 2026

This document provides a mapping between the Federal Committee on Statistical Methodology’s *A Framework for Data Quality* (FCSM 20-04, September 2020) and the National Institute of Standards and Technology’s *Artificial Intelligence Risk Management Framework* (NIST AI RMF 1.0, January 2023). It supports organizations operating at the intersection of federal statistical work and AI deployment, where data quality requirements and AI trustworthiness requirements must be satisfied simultaneously.

FCSM 20-04 organizes 11 data quality dimensions under three domains (Utility, Objectivity, Integrity) and provides the standard vocabulary for federal agencies evaluating data products under OMB Statistical Policy Directives and the Information Quality Act.

NIST AI RMF 1.0 defines seven characteristics of trustworthy AI and organizes risk management through four core functions (GOVERN, MAP, MEASURE, MANAGE) comprising 72 subcategories.

The crosswalk is presented in two directions:

- **Mapping A (pages 2-8):** For each FCSM 20-04 quality dimension, the relevant NIST AI RMF subcategories are identified.
- **Mapping B (pages 9-17):** For each NIST AI RMF subcategory, the relevant FCSM 20-04 quality dimensions are identified.

Where no substantive correspondence exists, “No equivalent subcategory/dimension” is noted. Partial correspondences, where one framework’s concern maps to part of the other’s, are indicated with an asterisk (*) and explanatory notes.

A companion article, *When AI Enters Federal Statistics: A Crosswalk Between Data Quality and AI Trustworthiness Frameworks* (Webb, 2026; DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.18766095](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18766095)), provides the analytical rationale for these mappings, identifies the critical gap between the frameworks (domain-specific AI failure modes in statistical work), and demonstrates applied implementations.

Critical Gap

Neither framework addresses the domain-specific failure mode where these concerns intersect: an AI system confabulating a classification or consultation response that has no basis in the

underlying data. FCSM was not designed for this because its quality threats arise from data collection, processing, and estimation. NIST was not designed for this at the domain level because it evaluates system-level properties without specifying what validity means in any particular domain.

This gap is one of specification, not detection: both frameworks provide the vocabulary to name the concern, but neither provides the protocol to evaluate it in a specific federal statistical AI application. Addressing this gap requires both frameworks simultaneously, plus domain-specific validation methods.

Mapping A: FCSM 20-04 Quality Dimensions to NIST AI RMF Subcategories

UTILITY Domain

Relevance

Does the data product address current and potential user needs?

FCSM Concern	Relevant NIST AI RMF Subcategories
Data product addresses identified user needs	No equivalent subcategory
Data product addresses anticipated future needs	No equivalent subcategory
Data product addresses needs across different user communities	No equivalent subcategory

Note: MAP 1.1, 1.3, 1.4, 3.1, and MANAGE 1.1 were considered but rejected. NIST AI RMF addresses relevance procedurally through the MAP function (defining context and intended use) and MANAGE 1.1 (intended purpose determination), but neither evaluates whether outputs serve user needs as a measurable output characteristic. FCSM treats Relevance as a quality dimension of the data product itself. An AI system can satisfy these procedural requirements while producing outputs that are irrelevant to actual user needs.

Accessibility

Can users obtain and understand the data product?

FCSM Concern	Relevant NIST AI RMF Subcategories
Users can locate and obtain the data product	No equivalent subcategory
Documentation is sufficient for users to understand the data product	No equivalent subcategory
Data products are available in formats suitable for diverse users	No equivalent subcategory
Metadata and supporting materials are provided	No equivalent subcategory

Note: GOVERN 4.2 and MEASURE 2.9 were considered but rejected. NIST addresses documentation of AI systems and outputs (under transparency and explainability) but does not address user access to outputs as a quality dimension. Accessibility in FCSM encompasses dissemination infrastructure, format suitability, and user support, all concerns outside NIST's system-trustworthiness scope.

Timeliness and Punctuality

Is the data current relative to user needs? Is it delivered on schedule?

FCSM Concern	Relevant NIST AI RMF Subcategories
Data is current relative to the time period it describes	No equivalent subcategory
Data products are released on the announced schedule	No equivalent subcategory
The lag between reference period and release is minimized	No equivalent subcategory

Note: NIST AI RMF does not address output currency or delivery schedules. Timeliness is a fitness-for-purpose judgment specific to data product dissemination that falls entirely outside the AI trustworthiness framework.

Granularity

Does the data provide sufficient detail for the intended use?

FCSM Concern	Relevant NIST AI RMF Subcategories
Data is available at appropriate levels of geographic, demographic, or subject-matter detail	No equivalent subcategory
Level of detail balances utility against confidentiality and reliability constraints	No equivalent subcategory

Note: MAP 3.3 and MAP 3.2 were considered but rejected. NIST addresses output scope (MAP 3.3) and error costs (MAP 3.2) but does not treat the resolution or level of detail of outputs as a quality dimension. FCSM Granularity encompasses the trade-off between detail and reliability, a concern that NIST addresses only indirectly through scope specification.

OBJECTIVITY Domain

Accuracy and Reliability

How close are estimates to true values? How consistent is measurement?

FCSM Concern	Relevant NIST AI RMF Subcategories
Estimates are close to true values (accuracy)	MEASURE 2.3: AI system performance or assurance criteria are measured qualitatively or quantitatively and demonstrated for conditions similar to deployment settings. MEASURE 2.5: The AI system to be deployed is demonstrated to be valid and reliable.
Measurement is consistent across replications (reliability)	MEASURE 2.5: The AI system is demonstrated to be valid and reliable. Limitations of generalizability are documented.
Sources of error are identified and quantified (Total Survey Error framework)	MEASURE 1.1: Approaches and metrics for measurement of AI risks are selected for implementation. Risks that cannot be measured are documented.

FCSM Concern	Relevant NIST AI RMF Subcategories
	MEASURE 2.1: Test sets, metrics, and details about TEVV tools are documented.
Error is managed within acceptable bounds	MANAGE 1.2: Treatment of documented AI risks is prioritized based on impact, likelihood, or available resources. MANAGE 1.3: Responses to high-priority AI risks are developed, planned, and documented.
Systematic error (bias in the statistical sense) is detected and corrected	MEASURE 2.11: Fairness and bias are evaluated and results are documented.* MAP 2.3: Scientific integrity and TEVV considerations are identified and documented, including construct validation.

**NIST's MEASURE 2.11 primarily addresses demographic fairness (systematically different outcomes based on protected characteristics). FCSM's concern with statistical bias (systematic measurement error) is a partial, not full, correspondence.*

Coherence

Are results consistent and comparable across sources, methods, and time?

FCSM Concern	Relevant NIST AI RMF Subcategories
Internal coherence: results are consistent within a data product	MEASURE 2.5: The AI system is demonstrated to be valid and reliable.
External coherence: results are comparable with other relevant sources	MEASURE 2.3: AI system performance or assurance criteria are demonstrated for conditions similar to deployment settings.
Temporal coherence: results are comparable over time	MANAGE 2.2: Mechanisms are in place to sustain the value of deployed AI systems. MANAGE 3.2: Pre-trained models used for development are monitored as part of regular monitoring and maintenance.

FCSM Concern	Relevant NIST AI RMF Subcategories
Methodological coherence: results from different methods are reconcilable	<p>MAP 2.3: Scientific integrity and TEVV considerations are identified and documented.</p> <p>MEASURE 2.13: Effectiveness of employed TEVV metrics and processes are evaluated and documented.</p>

Note: NIST addresses consistency as a component of validity and reliability but does not separately distinguish coherence as a quality dimension. Coherence evidence supports a validity claim in NIST terms but is not identical to it. FCSM's explicit treatment of cross-source, cross-method, and cross-time comparability as a named dimension has no structural parallel in NIST.

INTEGRITY Domain

Scientific Integrity and Credibility

Does the work adhere to accepted scientific methods? Is it shielded from inappropriate influence?

FCSM Concern	Relevant NIST AI RMF Subcategories
Methods adhere to accepted scientific standards	<p>MAP 2.3: Scientific integrity and TEVV considerations are identified and documented, including experimental design, data collection and selection, system trustworthiness, and construct validation.</p> <p>MEASURE 2.1: Test sets, metrics, and details about TEVV tools are documented.</p> <p>MEASURE 2.5: The AI system is demonstrated to be valid and reliable.</p> <p>MEASURE 2.13: Effectiveness of employed TEVV metrics and processes are evaluated.</p>

FCSM Concern	Relevant NIST AI RMF Subcategories
Work is shielded from political or other inappropriate influence	GOVERN 2.3: Executive leadership takes responsibility for decisions about risks associated with AI development and deployment. GOVERN 4.1: Organizational policies foster a critical thinking and safety-first mindset.
Methods and findings undergo appropriate review	MEASURE 1.3: Internal experts who did not serve as front-line developers and /or independent assessors are involved in regular assessments. MEASURE 4.1: Measurement approaches are connected to deployment contexts and informed through consultation with domain experts. MEASURE 4.2: Measurement results are informed by input from domain experts and relevant AI actors to validate consistent performance.
Limitations are honestly reported	MEASURE 2.5: Limitations of generalizability beyond development conditions are documented. GOVERN 4.2: Organizational teams document risks and potential impacts.

Transparency

Are methods, sources, limitations, and quality openly documented?

FCSM Concern	Relevant NIST AI RMF Subcategories
Methods are documented and publicly available	<p>GOVERN 1.4: The risk management process and its outcomes are established through transparent policies, procedures, and other controls.</p> <p>GOVERN 4.2: Organizational teams document risks and potential impacts and communicate broadly.</p> <p>GOVERN 4.3: Organizational practices are in place to enable AI testing, identification of incidents, and information sharing.</p>
Data sources are identified	<p>MAP 2.3: Scientific integrity and TEVV considerations are documented, including data collection and selection.</p> <p>MAP 4.1: Approaches for mapping AI technology and legal risks of components including third-party data are documented.</p>
Limitations and quality measures are reported	<p>MEASURE 2.5: Limitations of generalizability are documented.</p> <p>MEASURE 2.8: Risks associated with transparency and accountability are examined and documented.</p> <p>MEASURE 1.1: Risks that cannot be measured are properly documented.</p>
Changes to methods or sources are communicated	<p>MANAGE 4.3: Incidents and errors are communicated to relevant AI actors including affected communities.</p> <p>MANAGE 4.2: Measurable activities for continual improvements include regular engagement with interested parties.</p>

Confidentiality

Is respondent information protected from unauthorized disclosure?

FCSM Concern	Relevant NIST AI RMF Subcategories
Statistical disclosure limitation methods are applied	MEASURE 2.10: Privacy risk of the AI system is examined and documented.
Respondent information is protected from unauthorized access	GOVERN 6.1: Policies address AI risks associated with third-party entities.* MEASURE 2.7: AI system security and resilience are evaluated and documented.*
Disclosure risk from AI-mediated data access is managed	MEASURE 2.10: Privacy risk of the AI system is examined and documented. MAP 5.1: Likelihood and magnitude of each identified impact are identified and documented. MEASURE 2.6: AI system is evaluated regularly for safety risks.*

** Security and safety subcategories are listed as partial correspondences because FCSM Confidentiality is specifically about respondent information protection, while NIST's security and safety subcategories address broader system-level concerns. The correspondence holds where AI introduces new risk pathways (e.g., confidently wrong statistical guidance driving consequential policy or individual decisions).*

Computer and Physical Security

Is the system protected from unauthorized access, modification, or destruction?

FCSM Concern	Relevant NIST AI RMF Subcategories
Systems are protected from unauthorized access	MEASURE 2.7: AI system security and resilience are evaluated and documented. GOVERN 6.2: Contingency processes handle failures or incidents in third-party data or AI systems.

FCSM Concern	Relevant NIST AI RMF Subcategories
Data integrity is maintained against unauthorized modification	MEASURE 2.7: AI system security and resilience are evaluated and documented. MANAGE 2.3: Procedures respond to and recover from previously unknown risks.
Business continuity and disaster recovery are planned	MANAGE 2.4: Mechanisms are in place to supersede, disengage, or deactivate AI systems demonstrating inconsistent performance. MANAGE 4.1: Post-deployment monitoring plans include incident response, recovery, and change management.
Third-party system risks are managed	GOVERN 6.1: Policies address AI risks associated with third-party entities. GOVERN 6.2: Contingency processes for third-party failures are in place. MANAGE 3.1: AI risks from third-party resources are regularly monitored.

Objectivity of Presentation

Is information presented accurately, clearly, and without bias?

FCSM Concern	Relevant NIST AI RMF Subcategories
Information is presented accurately and clearly	MEASURE 2.8: Risks associated with transparency and accountability are examined and documented. MEASURE 2.9: AI system output is interpreted within its context to inform responsible use.
Presentation does not mislead or selectively emphasize	MEASURE 2.11: Fairness and bias are evaluated and documented.* MEASURE 2.9: AI model is explained, validated, and documented.

FCSM Concern	Relevant NIST AI RMF Subcategories
Uncertainty and limitations are communicated with results	MEASURE 2.5: Limitations of generalizability are documented. MEASURE 2.8: Transparency and accountability risks are examined.

** NIST MEASURE 2.11's fairness concern (systematically different outcomes by protected characteristics) partially overlaps with FCSM's presentation objectivity concern (unbiased presentation). The correspondence is partial: FCSM's "unbiased presentation" is broader than demographic fairness, encompassing any selective emphasis or framing that distorts interpretation.*

Mapping B: NIST AI RMF Subcategories to FCSM 20-04 Quality Dimensions

GOVERN Function

#	NIST AI RMF Subcategory	Description	Relevant FCSM Dimension(s)
1	GOVERN 1.1	Legal and regulatory requirements involving AI are understood, managed, and documented.	Transparency; Scientific Integrity/Credibility
2	GOVERN 1.2	Trustworthy AI characteristics are integrated into organizational policies, processes, and procedures.	Scientific Integrity/Credibility

#	NIST AI RMF Subcategory	Description	Relevant FCSM Dimension(s)
3	GOVERN 1.3	Processes determine the needed level of risk management activities based on organizational risk tolerance.	No equivalent dimension*
4	GOVERN 1.4	Risk management process and outcomes are established through transparent policies, procedures, and controls.	Transparency
5	GOVERN 1.5	Ongoing monitoring and periodic review of risk management process and outcomes are planned.	Accuracy & Reliability; Coherence
6	GOVERN 1.6	Mechanisms to inventory AI systems are in place and resourced.	No equivalent dimension‡
7	GOVERN 1.7	Processes for decommissioning and phasing out AI systems safely are in place.	No equivalent dimension‡
8	GOVERN 2.1	Roles and responsibilities for mapping, measuring, and managing AI risks are documented.	Transparency

#	NIST AI RMF Subcategory	Description	Relevant FCSM Dimension(s)
9	GOVERN 2.2	Personnel and partners receive AI risk management training.	Scientific Integrity/Credibility
10	GOVERN 2.3	Executive leadership takes responsibility for AI risk decisions.	Scientific Integrity/Credibility+
11	GOVERN 3.1	Decision-making is informed by a diverse team.	Scientific Integrity/Credibility
12	GOVERN 3.2	Policies define roles and responsibilities for human-AI configurations and oversight.	Scientific Integrity/Credibility
13	GOVERN 4.1	Organizational policies foster critical thinking and safety-first mindset.	Scientific Integrity/Credibility
14	GOVERN 4.2	Teams document risks and potential impacts and communicate broadly.	Transparency
15	GOVERN 4.3	Practices enable AI testing, incident identification, and information sharing.	Transparency; Scientific Integrity/Credibility
16	GOVERN 5.1	Policies collect and integrate feedback from those external to the development team.	Scientific Integrity/Credibility

#	NIST AI RMF Subcategory	Description	Relevant FCSM Dimension(s)
17	GOVERN 5.2	Mechanisms enable regular incorporation of adjudicated feedback into system design.	Scientific Integrity/Credibility; Accuracy & Reliability
18	GOVERN 6.1	Policies address AI risks associated with third-party entities.	Computer & Physical Security; Confidentiality*
19	GOVERN 6.2	Contingency processes handle failures in third-party data or AI systems.	Computer & Physical Security

* GOVERN 1.3 (organizational risk tolerance) is an AI governance concept without a direct FCSM analogue. FCSM addresses acceptable error bounds within specific quality dimensions but does not define organizational risk tolerance as a cross-cutting governance concept.

† GOVERN 2.3's concern with executive responsibility for AI risk maps to FCSM Scientific Integrity's requirement that work be shielded from inappropriate influence. The correspondence is that both require organizational structures that protect methodological independence.

MAP Function

#	NIST AI RMF Subcategory	Description	Relevant FCSM Dimension(s)
20	MAP 1.1	Intended purposes, beneficial uses, context-specific laws, and prospective settings are understood and documented.	Transparency

#	NIST AI RMF Subcategory	Description	Relevant FCSM Dimension(s)
21	MAP 1.2	Interdisciplinary AI actors with diverse competencies establish context.	Scientific Integrity/Credibility
22	MAP 1.3	Organization's mission and goals for AI technology are understood and documented.	No equivalent dimension*
23	MAP 1.4	Business value or context of business use is clearly defined.	No equivalent dimension*
24	MAP 1.5	Organizational risk tolerances are determined and documented.	No equivalent dimension*
25	MAP 1.6	System requirements are elicited from and understood by relevant AI actors.	Scientific Integrity/Credibility; Transparency
26	MAP 2.1	Specific tasks and methods the AI system will support are defined.	Scientific Integrity/Credibility; Transparency
27	MAP 2.2	AI system knowledge limits and human oversight of outputs are documented.	Transparency; Accuracy & Reliability

#	NIST AI RMF Subcategory	Description	Relevant FCSM Dimension(s)
28	MAP 2.3	Scientific integrity and TEVV considerations are documented, including experimental design, data collection and selection, system trustworthiness, and construct validation.	Scientific Integrity/Credibility; Accuracy & Reliability; Coherence
29	MAP 3.1	Potential benefits of intended AI functionality are examined and documented.	No equivalent dimension*
30	MAP 3.2	Potential costs from AI errors or system functionality are examined and documented.	Accuracy & Reliability
31	MAP 3.3	Targeted application scope is specified and documented.	No equivalent dimension*
32	MAP 3.4	Processes for operator and practitioner proficiency are defined and documented.	Scientific Integrity/Credibility
33	MAP 3.5	Processes for human oversight are defined and documented.	Scientific Integrity/Credibility

#	NIST AI RMF Subcategory	Description	Relevant FCSM Dimension(s)
34	MAP 4.1	Approaches for mapping AI technology and legal risks of components including third-party data are documented.	Transparency; Computer & Physical Security
35	MAP 4.2	Internal risk controls for AI system components including third-party technologies are documented.	Computer & Physical Security
36	MAP 5.1	Likelihood and magnitude of each identified impact are documented.	Confidentiality; Accuracy & Reliability
37	MAP 5.2	Practices for regular engagement with relevant AI actors and integrating feedback are documented.	Scientific Integrity / Credibility

** MAP 1.5 (organizational risk tolerance) has no FCSM equivalent (see note at GOVERN 1.3). MAP 3.2's correspondence with Granularity is partial: FCSM Granularity addresses level-of-detail trade-offs, while MAP 3.2 addresses cost-of-error assessment broadly.*

MEASURE Function

#	NIST AI RMF Subcategory	Description	Relevant FCSM Dimension(s)
38	MEASURE 1.1	Approaches and metrics for AI risk measurement are selected. Risks that cannot be measured are documented.	Accuracy & Reliability; Transparency
39	MEASURE 1.2	Appropriateness of AI metrics and effectiveness of controls are regularly assessed and updated.	Accuracy & Reliability; Coherence
40	MEASURE 1.3	Independent assessors and domain experts are involved in regular assessments.	Scientific Integrity/Credibility
41	MEASURE 2.1	Test sets, metrics, and TEVV tool details are documented.	Scientific Integrity/Credibility; Transparency
42	MEASURE 2.2	Evaluations involving human subjects meet applicable requirements and are representative.	Scientific Integrity/Credibility; Accuracy & Reliability
43	MEASURE 2.3	Performance or assurance criteria are measured and demonstrated for conditions similar to deployment.	Accuracy & Reliability; Coherence

#	NIST AI RMF Subcategory	Description	Relevant FCSM Dimension(s)
44	MEASURE 2.4	Functionality and behavior of AI system and components are monitored in production.	Accuracy & Reliability; Coherence
45	MEASURE 2.5	AI system is demonstrated valid and reliable. Generalizability limitations are documented.	Accuracy & Reliability; Coherence; Transparency
46	MEASURE 2.6	AI system is evaluated for safety risks. System is demonstrated safe, and can fail safely.	No equivalent dimension†
47	MEASURE 2.7	AI system security and resilience are evaluated and documented.	Computer & Physical Security; Confidentiality*
48	MEASURE 2.8	Risks associated with transparency and accountability are examined and documented.	Transparency; Objectivity of Presentation
49	MEASURE 2.9	AI model is explained, validated, documented; output is interpreted within context.	Transparency; Objectivity of Presentation
50	MEASURE 2.10	Privacy risk of AI system is examined and documented.	Confidentiality

#	NIST AI RMF Subcategory	Description	Relevant FCSM Dimension(s)
51	MEASURE 2.11	Fairness and bias are evaluated and documented.	Accuracy & Reliability; <i>Objectivity of Presentation</i>
52	MEASURE 2.12	Environmental impact and sustainability of AI model training are assessed and documented.	No equivalent dimension‡
53	MEASURE 2.13	Effectiveness of employed TEVV metrics and processes are evaluated and documented.	Scientific Integrity / Credibility; Coherence
54	MEASURE 3.1	Approaches to regularly identify and track existing, unanticipated, and emergent AI risks are in place.	Accuracy & Reliability
55	MEASURE 3.2	Risk tracking approaches are considered where measurement techniques are unavailable.	No equivalent dimension‡
56	MEASURE 3.3	Feedback processes for end users to report problems and appeal system outcomes are established.	Scientific Integrity / Credibility

#	NIST AI RMF Subcategory	Description	Relevant FCSM Dimension(s)
57	MEASURE 4.1	Measurement approaches are connected to deployment contexts and informed by domain expert consultation.	Scientific Integrity/Credibility; Accuracy & Reliability
58	MEASURE 4.2	Measurement results are informed by domain expert and AI actor input to validate consistent performance.	Scientific Integrity/Credibility; Coherence
59	MEASURE 4.3	Measurable performance improvements or declines based on consultations and field data are documented.	Accuracy & Reliability; Coherence

+ MEASURE 2.6 (safety) addresses whether a system endangers human life, health, property, or environment. FCSM operates in contexts where data products inform decisions but do not directly create physical safety risks. However, when AI mediates access to statistical data, the primary safety risk is confabulation: confidently wrong statistical guidance driving consequential policy or individual decisions. This is discussed in the companion article.

** MEASURE 2.7's correspondence with Confidentiality is partial (see note at Confidentiality mapping above). MEASURE 2.11's correspondence with FCSM is partial on both sides: NIST addresses demographic fairness (protected characteristics); FCSM addresses statistical bias (systematic measurement error) under Accuracy & Reliability and presentation bias under Objectivity of Presentation. These are related but distinct concerns. MEASURE 3.3's correspondence with Accessibility is partial: end-user feedback mechanisms relate to but are not equivalent to FCSM's data product accessibility concerns.*

MANAGE Function

#	NIST AI RMF Subcategory	Description	Relevant FCSM Dimension(s)
60	MANAGE 1.1	Determination is made whether AI system achieves its intended purpose and whether development or deployment should proceed.	Accuracy & Reliability
61	MANAGE 1.2	Treatment of documented AI risks is prioritized based on impact, likelihood, or available resources.	Accuracy & Reliability
62	MANAGE 1.3	Responses to high-priority AI risks are developed, planned, and documented.	Accuracy & Reliability; Scientific Integrity / Credibility
63	MANAGE 1.4	Negative residual risks to downstream acquirers and end users are documented.	Transparency; Accuracy & Reliability
64	MANAGE 2.1	Resources to manage AI risks are considered along with viable non-AI alternatives.	No equivalent dimension*
65	MANAGE 2.2	Mechanisms sustain the value of deployed AI systems.	Accuracy & Reliability; Coherence

#	NIST AI RMF Subcategory	Description	Relevant FCSM Dimension(s)
66	MANAGE 2.3	Procedures respond to and recover from previously unknown risks.	Computer & Physical Security; Accuracy & Reliability
67	MANAGE 2.4	Mechanisms to supersede, disengage, or deactivate underperforming AI systems are in place.	Computer & Physical Security; Accuracy & Reliability
68	MANAGE 3.1	AI risks from third-party resources are regularly monitored with documented risk controls.	Computer & Physical Security; Confidentiality*
69	MANAGE 3.2	Pre-trained models used for development are monitored as part of regular monitoring and maintenance.	Coherence; Accuracy & Reliability
70	MANAGE 4.1	Post-deployment monitoring plans include mechanisms for input capture, appeal, decommissioning, incident response, and change management.	Computer & Physical Security; Accuracy & Reliability

#	NIST AI RMF Subcategory	Description	Relevant FCSM Dimension(s)
71	MANAGE 4.2	Measurable activities for continual improvement include regular engagement with interested parties.	Transparency; Accuracy & Reliability; Coherence
72	MANAGE 4.3	Incidents and errors are communicated to relevant AI actors including affected communities.	Transparency

* *MANAGE 3.1's correspondence with Confidentiality is partial: monitoring third-party resources may encompass respondent data protection but is not specifically directed at it.*

‡ *These subcategories address AI system governance and lifecycle management activities (inventory, decommissioning, environmental impact, risk tracking without measurement) that fall outside FCSM's scope. FCSM evaluates properties of data products, not organizational processes for managing AI systems.*

Summary of Correspondences

FCSM Dimensions with No Equivalent NIST Subcategory

- **Relevance:** NIST addresses context documentation procedurally (MAP 1.1, 1.3, 1.4, 3.1) and intended purpose determination (MANAGE 1.1) but does not evaluate whether outputs serve user needs. Subcategories were considered and rejected.
- **Accessibility:** NIST addresses system documentation (GOVERN 4.2, MEASURE 2.9) but not user access to data products. Subcategories were considered and rejected.
- **Timeliness/Punctuality:** Output currency and delivery schedules are outside NIST's scope.
- **Granularity:** NIST addresses scope specification (MAP 3.3, 3.2) but not level-of-detail trade-offs in outputs. Subcategories were considered and rejected.

NIST Subcategories with No Equivalent FCSM Dimension

- **GOVERN 1.3:** Organizational risk tolerance as a governance concept

- **GOVERN 1.6:** AI system inventory mechanisms
- **GOVERN 1.7:** AI system decommissioning processes
- **MAP 1.5:** Organizational risk tolerance determination
- **MEASURE 2.6:** Safety risk evaluation (endangerment of human life, health, property)†
- **MEASURE 2.12:** Environmental impact of AI model training
- **MEASURE 3.2:** Risk tracking where measurement techniques are unavailable

†Safety is relevant in federal statistical contexts where AI-mediated access to data creates emergent risks: specifically, confidently wrong statistical guidance driving consequential policy or individual decisions. See companion article.

Key Partial Correspondences Requiring Domain Judgment

- **FCSM Accuracy & Reliability and NIST MEASURE 2.11 (Fairness/Bias):** FCSM addresses statistical bias (systematic measurement error); NIST addresses demographic fairness (systematically different outcomes by protected characteristics). Both are forms of bias. In federal statistical AI, epistemic bias (systematic classification error) is often more immediately relevant than demographic bias.
- **FCSM Confidentiality and NIST MEASURE 2.7 (Security) and MEASURE 2.6 (Safety):** FCSM addresses respondent information protection specifically. NIST addresses system security and safety broadly. The correspondence tightens when AI introduces new disclosure pathways not present in non-AI data dissemination.
- **FCSM Scientific Integrity and NIST GOVERN/MAP/MEASURE (multiple):** FCSM treats scientific integrity as a single dimension encompassing methodological soundness, independence from influence, and peer review. NIST distributes these concerns across multiple subcategories in multiple functions. No single NIST subcategory captures the full FCSM dimension.